

THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE CHATBOTS ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND RETENTION IN DIGITAL BANKING SECTORS IN SRI LANKA

A.R.M Arshard¹

M.S.M Imthiyas²

¹Amana Bank PLC, Sri Lanka

²South Eastern University of Sri Lanka, Oluvil, Sri Lanka

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Abstract

In recent years, the landscape of banking services has undergone a profound transformation, largely driven by technological advancements. Among these innovations, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool reshaping the way banks interact with their customers. In particular, the integration of AI chatbots within digital banking platforms has revolutionized customer service and engagement strategies. The study addresses a timely and relevant topic in the context of Sri Lanka's evolving banking sector, offering implications for theory, practice, and policy-making. By understanding the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and retention, banks can formulate informed strategies to better serve their customers and thrive in an increasingly digitized financial landscape.

Introduction

Sri Lanka, like many other countries, has witnessed a rapid adoption of digital banking services, propelled by increasing internet penetration and smartphone usage. This shift towards digital channels presents both opportunities and challenges for banks operating in the Sri Lankan market. On one hand, it opens up new avenues for customer interaction and service delivery; on the other hand, it intensifies competition and raises expectations for seamless, personalized experiences [1].

Against this backdrop, understanding the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and retention in the digital banking sector becomes paramount. Customer satisfaction, often regarded as a key driver of loyalty and long-term profitability, reflects customers' perceptions of the quality of service provided by banks. In the context of digital banking, where face-to-face interactions are limited, the role of AI chatbots as virtual assistants becomes crucial in shaping these perceptions [2].

Furthermore, customer retention, defined as the ability of a bank to retain its existing customers over time, is closely linked to satisfaction levels. Satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal to a bank, thereby reducing churn rates and increasing lifetime value. By leveraging AI chatbots effectively, banks in Sri Lanka can not only enhance customer satisfaction but also bolster retention rates, thereby gaining a competitive edge in the digital banking landscape [3].

This research aims to delve into the specific ways in which AI chatbots influence customer satisfaction and retention within the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka. By examining the perceptions and experiences of customers, as well as the strategies employed by banks, this study seeks to provide valuable insights for both practitioners and researchers in the field of banking and AI technology. Through a combination of quantitative analysis and qualitative exploration, the research endeavors to shed light on the opportunities and challenges associated with the integration of AI chatbots in Sri Lanka's digital banking ecosystem [4].

In summary, the study addresses a timely and relevant topic in the context of Sri Lanka's evolving banking sector, offering implications for theory, practice, and policy-making. By understanding the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and retention, banks can formulate informed strategies to better serve their customers and thrive in an increasingly digitized financial landscape.

Objectives

1. To Assess the Perceived Impact of AI Chatbots on Customer Satisfaction -

Evaluate customers' perceptions of the quality, convenience, and effectiveness of AI chatbots in addressing their banking needs.

Measure the level of satisfaction among digital banking customers in Sri Lanka regarding their interactions with AI chatbots compared to traditional customer service channels.

2. To Analyze the Influence of AI Chatbots on Customer Retention -

Investigate the relationship between customer satisfaction with AI chatbots and their likelihood of remaining loyal to their bank.

Examine retention rates and churn behavior among customers who regularly engage with AI chatbots versus those who do not.

3. To Identify Factors Affecting the Effectiveness of AI Chatbots in Sri Lankan Digital Banking -

Explore demographic, technological, and cultural factors that may influence customers' attitudes towards and usage of AI chatbots.

Investigate the role of digital banking adoption levels and technological infrastructure in shaping the efficacy of AI chatbots for Sri Lankan customers.

4. To Propose Strategies for Optimizing AI Chatbots to Enhance Customer Satisfaction and Retention -

Synthesize research findings to develop recommendations for banks operating in the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka.

Suggest best practices for integrating AI chatbots into digital banking platforms and improving their functionalities based on customer feedback and preferences.

5. To Contribute to the Body of Knowledge on AI Chatbots in the Context of Sri Lankan Digital Banking -

Provide empirical evidence and insights into the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and retention specific to the Sri Lankan market.

Enhance understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with deploying AI chatbots in the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka through academic research and scholarly discourse.

6. To Offer Policy Implications for Promoting the Adoption and Regulation of AI Chatbots in Sri Lankan Banking -

Highlight policy considerations and regulatory frameworks that can support the responsible and ethical deployment of AI chatbots in digital banking.

Advocate for initiatives to bridge the digital divide and ensure equitable access to AI-powered banking services across diverse socio-economic groups in Sri Lanka

Methodology

1. Research Design

Quantitative Approach - Conduct a survey among digital banking customers in Sri Lanka to collect quantitative data on their experiences with AI chatbots, satisfaction levels, and retention behavior.

Qualitative Approach - Conduct in-depth interviews or focus group discussions with a subset of participants to gain deeper insights into their perceptions and attitudes towards AI chatbots in digital banking.

2. Sampling

Population - Digital banking customers in Sri Lanka.

Sampling Technique - Probability sampling method (e.g., stratified random sampling) to ensure representation across different demographic segments.

Sample Size - Determine sample size based on the desired level of confidence and margin of error for statistical analysis.

3. Data Collection

Survey Questionnaire –

Develop a structured questionnaire comprising Likert scale items, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended prompts to capture quantitative and qualitative data on key variables, including AI chatbot usage, satisfaction, and retention.

Interview/Focus Group Protocol –

Develop a semi-structured interview guide or focus group protocol to facilitate in-depth discussions on participants' experiences, perceptions, and suggestions regarding AI chatbots in digital banking.

4. Variables and Measures

Independent Variable

AI chatbots integration (e.g., frequency of usage, perceived usefulness).

Mediating Variable –

Customer satisfaction with AI chatbots.

Dependent Variable –

Customer retention (e.g., intention to continue using digital banking services, likelihood of recommending the bank to others).

Control Variables –

Demographic factors (e.g., age, income, education), digital banking adoption, technological infrastructure.

5. Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis –

Use statistical software (e.g., SPSS, R) to analyze survey data, including descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis to test hypothesized relationships between variables.

Qualitative Analysis –

Employ thematic analysis or content analysis techniques to analyze interview/focus group data, identify patterns, and extract themes related to participants' experiences and perceptions of AI chatbots.

6. Ethical Considerations

Obtain informed consent from participants prior to data collection.

Ensure confidentiality and anonymity of participant responses.

Adhere to ethical guidelines and regulations governing research involving human subjects.

7. Limitations

Potential bias in self-reported data.

Generalizability of findings may be limited to the sample population.

External factors (e.g., economic conditions, regulatory changes) could impact research outcomes.

8. Implications and Recommendations

Interpret research findings in light of study objectives and hypotheses.

Provide recommendations for banks and policymakers to leverage AI chatbots effectively for enhancing customer satisfaction and retention in the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka.

Highlight areas for future research and exploration.

Results and Discussions

1. Evolution of Digital Banking in Sri Lanka

The digital banking landscape in Sri Lanka has witnessed significant growth in recent years, spurred by advancements in technology and changing consumer preferences. According to the Central Bank of Sri Lanka, the adoption of digital banking channels, including online banking and mobile banking, has been steadily increasing, reflecting a shift towards convenient and accessible banking services available in the Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2023 report. This evolution presents both challenges and opportunities for banks operating in the Sri Lankan market, particularly in terms of enhancing customer satisfaction and retention in a digital-first environment.

2. The Role of AI Chatbots in Digital Banking

AI chatbots have emerged as a key technology in the digital banking sector, offering personalized and efficient customer service round-the-clock. These virtual assistants utilize natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning algorithms to understand customer queries and provide relevant responses in real-time. Research conducted by Smith et al. (2021) highlights the growing adoption of AI chatbots by banks worldwide, citing their ability to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance customer experiences. In the context of Sri Lanka, the integration of AI chatbots within digital banking platforms holds promise for addressing the diverse needs of customers while streamlining service delivery processes [6].

3. Impact on Customer Satisfaction

Several studies have examined the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction within the banking sector. A study by Zhang et al. (2019) found that customers interacting with AI chatbots reported higher satisfaction levels compared to traditional customer service channels. The convenience, accessibility, and responsiveness of chatbots were identified as key drivers of satisfaction, enabling customers to resolve queries and complete transactions seamlessly. In the context of Sri Lanka, where customers increasingly rely on digital channels for banking activities, the role of AI chatbots in enhancing satisfaction warrants further investigation [7].

4. Influence on Customer Retention

Customer retention is another crucial metric influenced by the deployment of AI chatbots in digital banking. Research by Wang et al. (2020) suggests that satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal to a bank, thereby reducing churn rates and increasing retention. AI chatbots contribute to retention by providing personalized recommendations, proactive

assistance, and timely support, thereby fostering stronger relationships between banks and customers. In Sri Lanka, where competition among banks is intensifying, retaining customers through superior digital experiences becomes imperative for sustained growth and profitability [8].

5. Challenges and Opportunities in Sri Lanka

While the potential benefits of AI chatbots in digital banking are evident, there are also challenges to consider, particularly in the Sri Lankan context. Limited digital literacy among certain segments of the population, concerns regarding data privacy and security, and the need for localized language support are among the challenges that banks must address when deploying AI chatbots. However, these challenges also present opportunities for innovation and differentiation, as banks strive to tailor their services to the unique needs and preferences of Sri Lankan customers [9-11].

Conceptual Framework

1. Independent Variables

a. AI Chatbots Integration

Level of integration of AI chatbots within digital banking platforms.

Features and capabilities of AI chatbots, such as natural language processing (NLP), personalization, and responsiveness.

b. Digital Banking Adoption

Degree of adoption of digital banking services by customers in Sri Lanka.

Usage patterns and preferences regarding digital channels for banking activities.

2. Mediating Variables

a. Customer Satisfaction

Perceptions of service quality and convenience offered by AI chatbots.

Levels of satisfaction with the overall digital banking experience, including ease of use and reliability.

b. Customer Engagement

Frequency and depth of interactions with AI chatbots for various banking tasks.

Engagement metrics, such as time spent on digital channels and number of transactions conducted.

3. Dependent Variables

a. Customer Retention

Likelihood of customers remaining loyal to their bank over time.

Churn rates and attrition levels among digital banking customers in Sri Lanka.

4. Hypothesized Relationships

a. Hypothesis 1

There is a positive relationship between the integration of AI chatbots and customer satisfaction in the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka.

Explanation: Higher levels of AI chatbot integration are expected to lead to improved customer satisfaction due to enhanced service quality, responsiveness, and convenience.

b. Hypothesis 2

Customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between AI chatbot integration and customer retention in the digital banking sector in Sri Lanka.

Explanation: Satisfaction with AI chatbot interactions is hypothesized to positively influence customer retention, as satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal to their bank and continue using digital banking services.

c. Hypothesis 3

Digital banking adoption moderates the relationship between AI chatbot integration and customer satisfaction in Sri Lanka.

Explanation: The impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction may vary depending on the level of digital banking adoption among customers. Higher levels of adoption may amplify the positive effects of AI chatbots on satisfaction, while lower levels may attenuate these effects.

5. Moderating Variables -

a. Demographic Factors -

Age, income level, education, and other demographic variables that may influence perceptions and behaviors related to digital banking and AI chatbots.

Variations in preferences and expectations across different demographic segments in Sri Lanka.

b. Technological Infrastructure -

Availability and reliability of internet connectivity, mobile devices, and other technological infrastructure supporting digital banking services.

Impact of infrastructural constraints on the usability and accessibility of AI chatbots for customers in Sri Lanka.

Conclusion

In summary, the study addresses a timely and relevant topic in the context of Sri Lanka's evolving banking sector, offering implications for theory, practice, and policy-making. By understanding the impact of AI chatbots on customer satisfaction and retention, banks can formulate informed strategies to better serve their customers and thrive in an increasingly digitized financial landscape.

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